

The Dancer as Coder: Live Coding in Telematic Dance With Sensors

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of telematic dance projects combining live coding with embodied performance using sensors. It discusses the projects in the context of recent performances realized between Greece and Japan. It presents *sc-hacks-redux*, a SuperCollider library that enables live coding of the sound vocabulary as well as the interaction mode between dancers and sound producing algorithms, through the broadcasting sensor data as well as code using the open-source software *OscGroups*. The paper focusses on collaborative aspects, and on the interaction between data and code in the creation process. While coding on the keyboard radically differs from dancing as computer interaction modality, it can be argued that the live combination of recorded movement data with code opens new possibilities to interpret dance movement as a complement to code. Recorded movement data take the place of code in capturing reproducible aspects of performance, and in this way bring dancers closer to coding. We describe different strategies used to create performances, and the role of dancers/choreographers vs coders in the design process. Finally we discuss tools created to help dancers themselves to select sounds, refine interaction parameters and rehearse while independently running the library on their own computers during networked rehearsals.

1 Introduction

Live coding and performing with non-textual body movements through motion tracking are music performance modalities with contrasting characteristics and affordances. Live coders can specify algorithms describing sound structures of arbitrary complexity with high precision by inputting code over the keyboard. Unlike keyboard input, gesture-based input relies on movements measured by sensors to convey sequences of parameter values, commonly referred to as gestures. The shapes of gestures input from body movement via sensors can hardly match the accuracy of code-defined algorithms input as text on the keyboard. On the other hand, as Armitage has noted (2017), “(In live coding:) *The physical connection of the performer and their interface is limited to a small surface area of skin making singular temporal connections, one by one, with a computer keyboard.*” Yet it can be argued that gestural input affords a greater directness, variety, and expressive power, because it enables performers to define shades of musical expression through the shapes of body movements more freely and directly than by coding generative processes over the keyboard. In recent years, researchers recognizing the complementarity of these two modes of musical interaction through the computer have conducted several noteworthy attempts to introduce embodied gestures into live coding performances. These range from foundational studies (Baalman 2015; Diapoulis 2023), over works using gestural interfaces (Joanne Armitage 2016; Jack Armitage and McPherson 2017; Salazar 2017), to exploratory workshops investigating the potential of embodiment in live coding (Salazar and Armitage 2018). The present study documents a project which explores the potential of gestural interaction coupled to live coding under the combined criteria of two radical premises or objectives: (a) to extend the interaction paradigm of live coding through intimate coupling to human body movement using wearable sensor devices and (b) to create joint performances between two or more dancers and musicians situated in distant locations (Zannos and Carlé 2018) (figure 1).

In this project the dancers control sound generation through IMU (Inertial Motion Unit) sensors, which transmit measurements made by accelerometers on three axes wirelessly to SuperCollider (see figure 2). This enables performers to influence the generation of sound directly through their movements, and thus to participate in performance not only as dancers accompanying a musical piece, but as co-creators of the music itself together with programmers / live coders defining the interactive sonic framework of the performance. Control of sound structures through dance represents a departure from the classical instrumental paradigm both in terms of the relationship of the performer to the sound structure, which is more fluid and direct but at the same time less predictable and more complex. The dynamics of sound control through movement connected to live coding of synthesis algorithms create a new way of interaction and interpretation during performance, a kind of hybrid between dance, gestural music expression, and instrumental performance. This type of performance can be therefore be considered as an extension of dance into a new hybrid and experimental performance medium.

Figure 1: *Joint performance between Tokyo and Elevisis (Stage snapshot from Elevisis with zoom-image from Tokyo projected in the background).*

Figure 2: *sense/stage wireless sensor system by Marije Baalman with battery and pocket for wearing.*

Sound is rendered independently on SuperCollider at each venue location, based on code and sensor data shared via OscGroups. Graphics and VR can run on independent platforms. The OscGroups server runs on a cloud service (Linode of Digital Ocean).

Figure 3: Architecture of Networked Performance: Sharing Sensor Data and Code with OscGroups and rendering sound and image locally.

Previous papers document the project at various stages of its development (Zannos and Carlé 2018; Zannos 2019; Zannos and Hirayama 2023; Zannos and Dimitrakopoulou 2023). The present paper gives an overview of the system and summarizes the latest developments which resulted from the creation of works with dancers in remote collaboration. It discusses different strategies for gestural control, the role of gestural data recording and playback in combination with live coding, the creative work with dancers, and the need for tools to enable non-musician and non-programming dancers to work independently in order to develop choreographies. Close collaboration with dancers and visual artists necessitated in a shift of perspective and reevaluation of design priorities and strategies. Tools developed in close collaboration with the performers during the creation of the pieces were adapted to their particular needs as non-musicians and non-coders. The coding process was engaged in a continuous loop spanning the entire scope from framework design and implementation to off-line sound design to live development of sounds and interaction strategies, to development, teaching and testing of tools with dancers. This paper constitutes an attempt to trace the outlines of strategies that emerged in this process as new ways to attain a tight coupling between embodied performance and coding practices.

2 Infrastructure for Networked Performance

In this project both sensor data and program code driving a performance are shared between computers in real time. Sensor data as well as the code defining the sound behavior corresponding to those movements are transmitted over the internet using the Open Sound Control protocol (OSC). In this way the performance is replicated or shared between venues regardless of their actual physical distance. The implementation of this functionality is coded a SuperCollider library, *sc-hacks-redux* (found online at: <https://github.com/iani/sc-hacks-redux>). The library and uses the open source software OscGroups in order to broadcast both sensor data and program code to all computers in all participating venues (see figure 3).

The coder configures the mapping and routing of the sensor input from the dancers to the various rendering modules, by sending code to be evaluated by the local supercollider instance of each venue. In practice, the system makes it possible for a single user to run a performance remotely with multiple dancers performing on multiple remote locations. This approach is comparable to online game players sharing an experience in a virtual world, where the actions of each player are always transmitted to and reflected in the local systems of all other players, thereby creating a virtual space or game-universe shared by all players independently of their locations or gaming platform hardware. Sharing a common code workspace remotely places some severe constraints on the software infrastructure, which stem from the need to maintain consistency in workspaces running on separate computers and to be able to handle the structure of the shared workspace remotely by code. Additional requirements are raised by the need to give relative autonomy to remote performers to design and review performances even when located in a remote space on their own. Finally, is necessary to share designs and rehearsal material as files, and users should have access to that material locally. All of these needs above pose some fundamental design conditions, which the system was required to meet. Here is an brief outline of the solutions developed.

2.1 Namespaces for shared synthesis and control resources

The basic premise of a live coded embodied telematic performance is that code evaluated by any live coder in the network as well as data sent by any dancer in the network will run in all computers of the network. This creates the need to define a namespace for storing objects in each computer, and to keep the structure of that namespace identical in all computers, so that all objects needed for the performance coding can be accessed by name. Firstly, it should be possible to maintain namespaces for all resources and processes used in the performance. Such are: Buffers, busses, synths, and playing patterns or related processes such as routines. This means to be able to store any of these objects under names (Symbols) and to retrieve them. Additionally, it should be possible to store configurations of such objects containing all resources (busses, buffers, groups, synths etc.) in groups.

2.2 Use of a separate dictionary environment for each sound process

This principle follows one of the fundamental design patterns of *JITLib*, an early and widely used environment for live coding in SuperCollider (Rohrhuber, deCampo, and Wieser 2005). This is the idea of a *ProxySpace*, that is an environment where objects are stored as dictionary entries, and accessible to the user as environment variables when the *ProxySpace* is made current by the command “push”. The present library defines subclass of *EnvironmentRedirect*, called *Mediator* which responsible for storing sound processes and objects associated with them such as control busses, but behaves in a different way than *ProxySpace* in *JITLib*, as explained below.

2.3 Automatic stopping and replacement of processes

One of the first obstacles faced by live coders in SuperCollider is keeping track of sound processes stored in variables. When such a process is replaced by a new one, the reference to the old one can be lost, resulting in a hanging sound which cannot be stopped. To help in this, *Mediator* automatically stops a sound process when something else is stored in its place.

2.4 Operators for creating and modifying sound processes

The library operator such as `>` and `>>` as shortcuts for commands that convert a function or a dictionary of type *Event* into a sound signal synthesis process or a stream generating many sound events, and for modifying the state of sound syntheses or event streams.

2.5 Operators for accessing control busses and buffers

The basic principle of interaction design in any system that uses input from sensors is to design a mapping between the values of the parameters input from the sensors into parameter changes of the sound synthesis processes. This becomes rapidly complicated when many sensors with many parameters of possibly different value ranges are involved, because each of these must be mapped into parameter changes in possibly many different parameters of different sound synthesis processes. Additionally, mapping strategies are not just limited to linear or exponential scaling between value ranges, but may also involve logical decisions denoting state changes such as *on* or *off*, or translation into trigger events that initiate event state changes (start or stop a sound event). It is therefore necessary to separate processes that operate on signals to produce control signals or triggers from the processes that produce sound in response to control signals. For this reason, the *sc-hacks-redux* library of this project defines operators and shortcuts for accessing control busses, mainly denoted by use of the `@` mark (for example `@>`), and for defining signal processing processes operate on these. As a result of this distinction it is possible to separate the design of control signal processing from the design of sound signal synthesis, and to combine these by using as keys the names of busses pointing to control signals. One future potential of this approach to be explored is the possibility to design information processing networks in a manner resembling artificial neural networks.

2.6 Modification of patterns on the fly

The pattern playing mechanism for *Pbind* creates a routine that has no access to the keys of the *Pbind* from which it was created. This makes it difficult to modify a *Pbind* while it is running. While *JITLib* provides means for modifying keys, such as *Pbinddef*, these require coding for each key separately and are generally somewhat cumbersome to handle. To solve this problem, the *sc-hacks-redux* library uses its own class *EventStream*, which can modify playing instances

of itself while they are playing. This makes it possible to modify players stored in the Mediator environment easily. Additionally, it is possible to exchange between playing synths and playing patterns in the same key. Example:

```
() +> \play; // start an empty event as pattern with default key values
// set the degree key:
(degree: (0..10).pseq) ++> \play; // ++> modify without replacing
(dur: 0.1) ++> \play; // set the dur key
(degree: (0..10).prand) ++> \play; // modify the degree key
{ SinOsc.ar(500, 0, 0.1).dup } +> \play; // replace the pattern with a synth
```

2.7 Keeping track of resource state asynchronously: Use of Observer pattern protocol

Besides maintaining multiple namespaces for storing such objects and accessing them it is necessary to keep track of the states of the objects that are represented by the symbols in question, for example the running state of synths or patterns. For this, the library makes use of the existing infrastructure for the Observer pattern in SuperCollider. The Observer pattern is a widely used language pattern in Object Oriented Programming. It is based on the principle of a *notifier* object issuing a notification that it has changed, which is then received by any other objects that may need to respond to the changes in the *notifier*. While the basic Observer pattern mechanism exists in SuperCollider, it is not used widely and consistently, which results in diverse complicated and inconsistent mechanisms for tracking state. The *sc-hacks-redux* library introduces a new class *Notification* in order to implement this pattern over the entire system in a uniform manner. This replaces the existing class *NotificationCenter*, providing extended functionality such as access to notifications and modification of notification connections and making use of the built-in *changed / update* mechanism of the Observer pattern. This, together with use of the Library as means for storing resources in keys, creates a consistent system-wide infrastructure for monitoring state of objects asynchronously. The *Notification* class implements this pattern along with an API that enables one to easily define custom responses of any object to *changed* messages received from another object. This pattern is almost ubiquitously used in the library and serves as basis for designing both Graphical User Interfaces and for designing and customizing the behavior of the system in response to OSC messages. The implementation is based on the *Notification* class. This is inspired by the built-in *Notification*, the library defines operators and methods which enable the user to modify on the fly the response of the language to incoming OSC messages.

2.8 Dynamic definition of responses to OSC messages

Based on the Observer pattern protocol of the *Notification* class, the library defines operators and methods which enable the user to modify on the fly the response of the language to incoming OSC messages. Prominent examples include the evaluation of a message argument as code - enabling remote code evaluation from any user, the writing of a messages argument values into control busses, and the display of received messages in various ways. This forms a core tool enabling customization of the behavior of the system by coders in general, and will therefore form the second future focus of the present research along with information processing networks.

3 Infrastructure for Performance Development

Several windows were developed to enable easy tracking and management of the system state and data. Besides the main coder of the project (the author of this paper), these were also used in many occasions by assistants running workstations for remote performance venues as well as by the dancers themselves in rehearsals and in performances. Figure 4 shows a basic subset of these windows.

- *OscMonitor*: Access to main OSC functions of the system, such as OSC data sharing and monitoring, enabling and disabling of *OscGroups*, posting and monitoring of individual osc messages, and menus for opening scores and presets stored in the *sc-hacks-redux* repository.
- *Minibee*: Live display of incoming sensor data values from the sense/stage Minibee sensor system
- */minibee/data* : display of individual message input (opening by pressing enter on the selected message in the list view of the *OscMonitor* window).
- *230803_204306_JunAsayo3LONGall* browser for recording data including both sensor and code data.
- *../izutsu/sessions/* : Folder and file browser for opening score files with code and data, with menus for merging recording data from multiple files and for filtering osc messages or code.

Figure 4: Commonly used GUI windows: OscMonitor, Sensor Monitor, File Browser, Score Browser, Osc Message Monitor

3.1 Sharing project files, project browser

Code for multiple projects was shared in a separate repository (<https://github.com/iani/sc-projects>). A browser was developed for navigating this repository and opening files in it as scores containing snippets of code or messages. This was later generalized to run on any folder and its functionality was adapted to respond to the needs of the project as it evolved (see figure 5).

3.2 Code management and performance scores

Recorded sensor and code data from rehearsals was uploaded in github repository: https://github.com/iani/osc_data_230611ff. Making use of the basic tools mentioned above, the library provides a basic GUI framework for executing any of those files either as a whole, or in part based on a predefined separator syntax (//:). Furthermore, it is possible to play any such file as a score where each part or snippet has a predefined duration given in the comment header in the form of //:[duration]. This makes it possible to write scores as program files and to play these at any moment from the GUI. Figure ?? shows the score from a recorded rehearsal which was run by two dancers between Japan and Greece on their own computer and recorded by the author / main coder who was acting as consultant. The dancers could then replay the recorded data to review the rehearsal and propose improvements for the next stage.

The rehearsal above was guided by a separate gui which presented a repertory of buffers coupled with a menu for sound processing algorithms to select for each buffer, along with code for mapping data input from the sensors to synthesis parameters. This was a simple first contact to coding for the dancers who had very limited experience with computers and were handling the system on their own (figure 7).

Here is an excerpt of the code corresponding to the preset:

```
/*presets for asayo saved at 230913_203911*/

//: (0) asayo grainfroth crickets
//this is the template from mgrainfroth 230830_195041
//The source is: 230803_195659_JunAsayo3code
```


Figure 5: Project folder browser

Figure 6: Score of recorded rehearsal showing snippets with timestamps.

Figure 7: Gui for testing and generating soynD processing algorithms on a list of samples.

```

(
'amp': [ 1.0, "Xyz(5, 0.2, 0.3, 1.5)", 'on' ],
'buf': 'crickets',
'endframe': [ 1826955, nil, nil ],
'playfunc': 'grainfroth',
'pos': [ 0.079185223249971, "\\x5.sr", 'on' ],
'startframe': [ 9906, nil, nil ],
'trate': [ 0.17625899280576, "\\z5.sr", 'off' ],
'vol': [ 3.356638951877, "", 'off' ],
)
//: (1) asayo grainmagshift crickets
//This should be used in asayo's last solo as it is here.
//see also separate file copy of the preset 230913_asayo_finale_solo.scd
//It should be softened through resonant filters, rate and shift etc.!!!
(
'amp': [ 0.66674861549609, "Xyz(5, 1.0, 0.15, 1.0) + Xyz(8, 1.0, 0.15, 1.0)", 'on' ],
'buf': 'crickets',
'endframe': 2451380,
'pan': [ 0.48920863309353, "", 'off' ],
'playfunc': 'grainmagshift',
'pos': [ 0.21942446043165, "\\x5.sr", 'on' ],
'rate': [ 0.56001729413614, "\\z8.sr.lin(0.25, 0.9).round(0.1);", 'off' ],
'shift': [ 0.0, "\\x5.sr.lin(-480, -420).lag(0.5).round(0.1);", 'off' ],
'startframe': 0,
'stretch': [ 1.0161870503597, "\\x8.sr.lin(1.1, 1.5).lag(0.5).round(0.1);", 'off' ],
'trate': [ 3.8314873847371, "\\z8.sr", 'off' ],
'vol': [ 8.4137725790591, "", 'off' ],
)

```

The rehearsals led to a networked performance between Malta and Kyoto on September 28, 2023, and the score was further processed to form part of the networked performance between Elevisis and Tokyo on October 21st. A snapshot of the performance in Malta/Kyoto is found in figure 8.

4 Evaluation, Experiences, Conclusion

Embedding a live-coding practice in a project involving dancers with sensors and a networked collaboration with many artists led to the development of many tools and approaches in directions that could not have arisen without the feedback from the members of the project. Recording sensor data and interspersing these with code was a cornerstone in this approach. The main direction in which this project has progressed is towards a merging between code/score, embodied interaction and live coding. This seems to be the main profile of a new practice that is emerging from this field. There are examples of the code developed for these performances found in the repository at <https://github.com/iani/sc-projects> and more targeted examples in folder https://github.com/iani/sc-hacks-redux/tree/master/Pieces/MagneticDance/ENTIRE_SHOW231020b/D_IZUTSU. An analysis of the interaction strategies developed through this code would be beyond the scope of the present article. Videos of the works developed and the rehearsals done in the course of the project can be seen in the Youtube channel of the project at <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpLQo4OzAyGp3akEE3ho3bQ> and main examples are: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HXPeVC3PqqM> https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Mz2_rH3Cd-4 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f-1UJxMc490> and others. If anything, this work showed that collaborating between performance disciplines can bring new directions to coding and that coding relies on its social grounding in order to grow and thrive.

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Figure 8: Snapshot from the networked performance between Malta and Kyoto. Mary Rantou is in Malta and Yoshimitsu Yoshiya is seen from Kyoto over Zoom. Live graphics on openFrameworks by Vicky Bisbiki are driven from the live sensor data during the performance.

Justine Goussot, performers/dancers Yoshimitsu Yoshiya, Sakurako Shibata, Yang Chen, Composers and researchers Haruka Hirayama, Hideaki Isobe, Vasilis Agiomyrgianakis, and media artists Dana Papachristou, Vicky Bisbiki, Yang Pulaixin, Zhang Junkai, Quiao Quiao, Liu Tianqi, and Andrés Madrueño.

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